

C-SCALE

D3.5 Periodical assessment of the services V2

Status:	FINAL	Planned due date:	30/06/2022
Version:	1.1	Submission date:	26/09/2022
Lead Participant:	EGI Foundation	Lead Author:	Enol Fernández
Related WP:	WP3	Document Ref:	D3.5
Dissemination Level:	Public (PU)		
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7114582		

Deliverable Abstract

This report presents an update of the assessment of the C-SCALE services provided through the Virtual Access (VA) mechanism to the users. These include computing and storage resources. The deliverable describes the existing VA installations, their management within the project, updates the usage metrics delivered from the start of the project (January 2021) until Month 18 (June 2022) and reports on the Green Computing metrics and initiatives from the C-SCALE providers.

The current version (1.1) includes a few corrections from the version 1.0.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017529.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by parties of the C-SCALE consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

C-SCALE receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017529.

DELIVERY SLIP

Date	Name	Partner/Activity
Lead Author:	Enol Fernández (EF)	EGI Foundation
Contributors:	Zdeněk Šustr (ZS), Marcin Ziółkowski (MZ), Giacinto Donvito (GD), Hande Erdem (HE), Zacarias Benta (ZB), Charis Chatzikyriakou (CC), Mario David (MD), Raymond Oonk (RO), Nikos Triantafyllis (NT)	CESNET, CloudFerro, INFN, VITO, INCD, EODC, SURF, GRNET
Moderated by:	Enol Fernández (EF)	EGI Foundation
Reviewed by:	Andrea Manzi (AM)	EGI Foundation
	Benjamin Schumacher (BS)	EODC
Approved by:	C-SCALE Activity Management Board (AMB): Christian Briese (CB), Diego Scardaci (DS), Charis Chatzikyriakou (CC), Zdeněk Šustr (ZS), Enol Fernández (EF), Björn Backeberg (BB), Sebastian Luna-Valero (SLV)	EODC, CESNET, EGI Foundation, Deltares

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author(s)
V0.1	2022-06-17	Initial Version	EF, ZS, MZ, GD, HE, ZB, CC, MD, RO, NT
V0.2	2022-06-17	Added Green Computing metrics	EF
V0.3	2022-06-23	Incorporated feedback from reviewers	EF
V1.0	2022-06-30	Final version approved by AMB	C-SCALE AMB
V1.1	2022-09-26	Amended CloudFerro's Virtual Access metrics to fix mistakes detected during the periodic report	EF, LK, CC

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	2 of 21

Table of Contents

1	List of Tables	4
2	List of Acronyms.....	5
3	Executive Summary.....	7
4	Introduction.....	8
5	Virtual Access Metrics.....	10
6	Green Computing.....	19
7	Conclusions.....	21

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	3 of 21

1 List of Tables

Table 1. C-SCALE Installations per provider and category 8
Table 2. C-SCALE VA Agreements 10
Table 3. VA Usage 11
Table 4. VA Consumption..... 15
Table 5. Green Computing aspects of the providers 19

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	4 of 21

2 List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CO	Collaborative Organisation
C-SCALE	Copernicus - eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre (C-SCALE provider)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRNET	Greek Research and Technology Network (C-SCALE provider)
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HiSea	High Resolution Copernicus-Based Information Services at Sea for Ports and Aquaculture
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTDP	High Throughput Data Processing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
INCD-NCG	Infraestrutura Nacional de Computação Distribuída-National Computing Grid (C-SCALE provider)
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PBS	Portable Batch System
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PUE	Power usage effectiveness
REF	Renewable energy factor
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	5 of 21

STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TB	Terabyte
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	6 of 21

3 Executive Summary

C-SCALE brings together European commercial (e.g., Copernicus DIAS) and public computing and storage providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) use cases that deal with data- and compute-intensive workloads. The federation enables the access to a set of computing and storage resources, called *installations*, operated by the partners of the project and deployed via a Virtual Access mechanism. Almost 20% of the total C-SCALE budget is devoted to cover the costs of these installations that the project will deliver to EOSC users as services.

This deliverable updates the report provided in Month 14 (February 2022) – originally planned in Month 12 (December 2021) - on the usage of Virtual Access for C-SCALE providers. While all use cases are now onboarded and engaged with providers, the use cases are still under development with testing and piloting activities taking place. This kind of activity still does not produce large consumption of resources and the overall consumption of VA in the project is low. New use cases from the C-SCALE Open Call have been onboarded and the allocation of them to providers has been already agreed: two of these use cases (SAR on the fly and SPOTLIGHT) are already actively using resources, the rest will start later as the users get ready. As use cases become fully operational the usage of VA will reach the expected levels in the coming months.

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	7 of 21

4 Introduction

This deliverable provides the second assessment of the C-SCALE services based on the Virtual Access (VA) installations of the project, which provide the computing and storage resources that power the C-SCALE services that will be made available through EOSC. Deliverable D3.4 introduced the VA installations and the initial usage delivered until November 2021. In this document, we report the usage collected until the end of Month 18 (June 2022). The following deliverable D3.6 will provide an update on Month 24 (December 2022) and finally D3.7 will report the usage at the end of the project (June 2023). After the initial phase, where only the applications from the project use cases were accessing and consuming resources from the C-SCALE providers, in this updated version we report the accepted use cases from the Open Call and their planned consumption of resources.

There have not been any changes in the 23 installations from the C-SCALE providers since the start of the project, but a future amendment will fix some calculation errors in the VA installation description forms and add new installations to cover for new features requested by use cases. These changes are still under discussion and will be reported in D3.6. The current installations are described in more detail in D3.4 and summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1. C-SCALE Installations per provider and category

Provider	VA installation	Category	Mode of access	Unit of access
EODC	EODC EO storage	Storage	Secure Shell (ssh)	TB/year
	EODC EO Cloud	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack ¹ APIs	CPU/year
	EODC HPC	HPC/HTC	ssh	CPU/hour
CESNET	MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack API/GUI + PBS ²	CPU core/month
INFN	INFN Bari Storage	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB/month
	INFN Bari CPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	CPU core/month
SURF	SURFsara dCache Front end storage	Storage	ssh	TiByte*Year
	SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Year
	SURFsara Data Processing Compute	HPC/HTC	ssh	CPU*Hour
	SURFsara MS4 Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Year
	SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Month
	SURFsara MS4 Compute	Cloud IaaS	ssh	CPU*Hour
VITO	VITO CVB (Storage)	Storage	via Notebooks, VMs, openEO ³ API	TB/Month

¹ OpenStack is a Open Source Cloud Software, see <https://www.openstack.org/>

² Portable Batch System, a batch scheduling system, see <https://www.openpbs.org/>

³ openEO: an open API to connect to Earth observation cloud back-ends, see <https://openeo.org/>

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	8 of 21

	VITO CVB (CPU)	Cloud IaaS	SSH & openEO API	CPU/hour
GRNET	GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB*Hour
	GRNET KNS - Cloud	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	Core*Hour
	GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	Storage	ssh	TB*Hour
	GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	HPC/HTC	ssh	Core*Hour
CloudFerro	CREODIAS - Storage	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB/month
	CREODIAS - Compute	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	vCore/hour
	CREODIAS - GPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	VMGPU/hour
INCD	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB*month
	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	CPU*hour

Currently, these installations support use cases from WP4 and those use cases from the Open Call that are ready to deploy their workflows in the infrastructure. C-SCALE is working on the definition and on-boarding of two new services in EOSC: the Copernicus Data Processing Platform and the openEO Platform. Once onboarded, the installations will also be offered via the EOSC.

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	9 of 21

5 Virtual Access Metrics

Each installation of C-SCALE defines a set of metrics to report VA usage to the project, with clear description of the metrics and how the measurement is done by the provider. These metrics are reported on a 3-monthly basis to the internal project workspace (Confluence) by the providers.

C-SCALE implements an SLA (Service Level Agreement)/OLA (Operational Level Agreement) framework that tracks for all use cases the agreed number of resources and the conditions to access them. Currently, there are agreements in place for all the active use cases of C-SCALE: six use cases from WP4 and two use cases from the Open Call (SAR on the fly and SPOTLIGHT). These agreements are summarised in Table 2. Agreements for the Open Call use cases that will start later are still under negotiation, although the providers have been already identified and a draft document for each of them is available on C-SCALE workspace.

Table 2. C-SCALE VA Agreements

Use Case	Providers	Start date	End date
Aquamonitor	INCD, INFN	2021-06-01	2023-06-30
RETURN	SURF	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
LSDA	SURF	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
HiSea	GRNET	2021-08-01	2023-06-30
Wetland Water Stresses	EODC, CloudFerro	2021-11-01	2023-06-30
WaterWatch	CESNET, VITO	2022-02-01	2023-06-30
SAR on the fly	CloudFerro	2022-04-25	2023-06-30
SPOTLIGHT	EODC	2022-07-01	2023-06-30

The agreements are reviewed periodically (every 6 months) to ensure the allocations described in them are still valid and whenever there is a change in the support given to a use case. Most of the use cases of WP4 will go through a re-deployment phase where their applications will be scaled beyond a single provider, with the new providers to use for each use case defined during the project proposal. An update of the agreements to add these providers will take place in the coming months as the use cases become ready. The information in the agreements and the usage metrics from providers are used as input for the project's capacity management team formed by members of the *Operations of the Virtual Access installation* task (T3.4) and *Provider onboarding support and the VA coordination* task (T5.1). The team keeps track of the usage trends and reacts accordingly and plans the capacity allocation for the use cases to be supported.

Table 3 shows the cumulative metric values from the start of the project until M11 (as reported in D3.4) and until the end of M18 (June 2022), which is the last metrics collection before the writing of this deliverable. Following deliverables covering the assessment of the services (D3.6 and D3.7) will present the updated values for the metrics. As installations were not available before C-SCALE to EOSC users, the baseline value for all installations is 0.

Metrics related to number of users or number of use cases in Table 3 have been homogenized for Month 18 to show the number of use cases supported by each installation and, whenever available,

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	10 of 21

also the number of individual users belonging to the supported use cases. This facilitates the comparison of the uptake of providers as the number of individual users varies depending on the usage model of each use case: from use cases where a single to few expert users are in charge of the deployment of services that final researchers will access to use cases where each individual user interacts with the installations directly (e.g., by submitting jobs to a HPC system).

Table 3. VA Usage

VA Installation	Metric type	Description	Baseline	M01 - M11	M01-M18
EODC EO storage	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	0	1 use case
	Usage	Allocated TB/year	0	0	0.42 TB*year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	1
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	Austria
EODC EO Cloud	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	1	1 use case
	Usage	Time of VM usage	0	1.33 CPU/Year	10.64 CPU/Year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	1	1
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	0	Austria	Austria
EODC HPC	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	0	0
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	0
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	0
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	-
MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	Number of users	Number of user consuming CPU resources	0	0	1 use case (1 user)
	Usage	CPU core months consumed (with typically 4GB of RAM per core)	0	0	10 CPU core/month
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	1
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	Czechia

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	11 of 21

INFN Bari Storage	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	0
	Usage	TB used / month	0	0	0
INFN Bari CPU	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	0
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	0
SURFsara dCache Front end storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-
SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	14	2 use cases (18 users)
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	19.15 TB*Year	41.79 TB*year
	Satisfaction ⁴	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	4	5
SURFsara Data Processing Compute	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	14	2 use cases (18 users)
	Usage	Wall time CPU core hours consumed by C-SCALE users	0	143599 CPU*hours	247962 CPU*hours
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	4	4
SURFsara MS4 Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-
SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-

⁴ Measures customer satisfaction based on a feedback survey that grades services from 1-5 (being very dissatisfied and 5 being very satisfied)

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	12 of 21

SURFsara MS4 Compute	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Usage	Wall time CPU core hours consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-
VITO CVB (Storage)	Number of users	User that created an account and has actively logged into a VM or used an API service	0	0	0
	Usage	Time in months for VM usage and in hours for Hadoop usage	0	0	0
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries reached using our datawarehousing system	0	0	0
	Names of the countries reached		-	-	-
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of users	User that logged in to openEO	0	0	1 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Time in months for VM usage and in hours for Hadoop usage	0	0	16660 CPU Hours 66700 RAM GB-Hours
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of countries reached	Amount of countries reached using our datawarehousing system	0	0	0
	Names of the countries reached		-	-	-
GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	11	1 use case (11 users)
	Usage	Total number of TB Hours for the duration of the project	0	Disk GB-Hours - 372120.86	701.22 TB*Hours
GRNET KNS - Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	11	1 use case (11 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual CPU hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	0	93137.71 CPU*Hours	173794.05 Core*Hours

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	13 of 21

GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	5	1 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of TB hours for the duration of the project	0	1.364 TB*Hours	80.8 TB*Hours
GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	5	1 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of CPU core hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	0	170 Core*Hours	326 Core*Hours
CREODIAS - Storage	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	20 TB*Month
CREODIAS - Compute	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)
	usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	7866.76 vCPU*hours
CREODIAS - GPU	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	407.27 VMGPU*hours
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	Number of users	Total number of new users	0	4	1 use case (4 users)
	Usage	Total storage (unit TB*month) allocated to the project	0	62.015	159
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	0	1	1
	Names of the countries reached		-	The Netherlands	The Netherlands
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	Number of users	Total number of new users	0	4	1 use case (4 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual VCPU*hour with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the	-	310832	834992

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	14 of 21

		duration of the project			
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	0	1	1
	Names of the countries reached		-	The Netherlands	The Netherlands

Table 4 shows the consumption in percent of the available units for all the installations. As planned in the project, the VA usage during the initial months of the project has been mostly related to test activities to make the new federation access channels fully operational and to integrate the existing use cases. Those providers without any usage so far are already engaged with the use cases but were not yet delivering resources at the time of the metric collection.

Table 4. VA Consumption

Provider	VA installation	Available units	Consumed M1 - M18
EODC	EODC EO storage	150 TB/year	0.28%
	EODC EO Cloud	620 CPU/year	1.72%
	EODC HPC	600,000 CPU/hour	0.00%
CESNET	MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	2,850 CPU core/month	0.35%
INFN	INFN Bari Storage	1,500 TB/month	0.00%
	INFN Bari CPU	3,840 CPU core/month	0.00%
SURF	SURFsara dCache Front end storage	154 TiByte*Year	0.00%
	SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	160 TB*Year	26.11%
	SURFsara Data Processing Compute	1,500,000 CPU*Hour	16.53%
	SURFsara MS4 Storage	10 TB*Year	0.00%
	SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	96 TB*Month	0.00%
	SURFsara MS4 Compute	147,600 CPU*Hour	0.00%
VITO	VITO CVB (Storage)	266 TB/Month	0.00%
	VITO CVB (CPU)	292,000 CPU/hour	5.7%
GRNET	GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	250,000 TB*Hour	0.28%
	GRNET KNS - Cloud	1,650,000 Core*Hour	10.53%
	GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	219000 TB*Hour	0.03%
	GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	1,000,000 Core*Hour	0.03%
CloudFerro	CREODIAS - Storage	2,762 TB/month	8.4%

⁵ The original figure in VITO's installation had an error in the calculation. An amendment is currently under preparation to fix the errors. This report shows the corrected figures already.

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	15 of 21

	CREODIAS - Compute	1,500,000 vCore/hour	0.05%
	CREODIAS - GPU	6,000 VMGPU/hour	2.75%
INCD	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	450 TB*month	35.33 %
	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	3,240,000 CPU*hour	25.77%

The entire reported VA consumption of EODC's installations (EODC EO Storage and EODC EO Cloud) has occurred by the *Wetland Water Stresses* use case. This use case, which is run by TU Wien and is based in Austria, was onboarded to the EODC EO Cloud in November 2021 and to the EODC EO Storage in February 2022, and it expected to continue consuming resources until the end of the project (June 2023). In addition, for the *REcovery of Tropical Forest Using Radar seNtinel time series* (RETURN) use case, where EODC is providing access to higher level data, there has been still no VA usage recorded. Looking ahead, the new use case, *On-demand semantic EO data cubes*, which was onboarded in C-SCALE through the project's Open Call and is led by the Paris Lodron University Salzburg, is expected to start consuming resources from the EODC EO Storage and EODC EO Cloud starting in July 2022. Finally, the *High Resolution Land Surface Drought Analysis* (LSDA) use case is planned to be redeployed to EODC's HPC infrastructure in Quarter 3 of 2022. As a result, the usage of the available VA is expected to rise with the upcoming deployment of these use cases at EODC's premises.

CESNET has been supporting the WaterWatch use case. In the initial stages (until M18), mostly preparatory work has been carried out, setting up data discovery, fetching and cataloguing resources. Actual processing (compute) resources have not been instantiated so far, but there are allocated resources used in cataloguing near-real time Sentinel products with STAC.

INFN has started the support to the Aquamonitor community to access INFN resources focusing on leveraging the automation and orchestration capabilities of the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator. This will help to easily deploy the use case over heterogeneous Cloud infrastructures, both from EOSC providers like C-SCALE and EGI, or public providers like AWS, Azure, etc, without extra human effort and without the need to gain IT know-how on the underneath cloud solution. So far, the support to Aquamonitor has not produced significant VA consumption and the provider has not reported any usage.

SURF VA has been supporting the *REcovery of Tropical Forest Using Radar seNtinel time series* (RETURN) and *High Resolution Land Surface Drought Analysis* (LSDA) use cases in the period M1-18. Initially, the RETURN use case focused on Sentinel-2 (S2) and Landsat imaging data. A pipeline creating analysis ready data cubes has been fully deployed on the SURF data processing (HTC) infrastructure. However, due to changes in personnel, the RETURN use case has shifted its focus from S-2 to Sentinel-1 (S-1) radar data. This required significant human support by SURF for deployment as the S-1 processing and analysis chain has no overlap with the S-2 chain. This support

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	16 of 21

included debugging, recompilation, and deployment of the yeoda⁶ conda environment to fix some errors in the environment setup. These errors were resolved by SURF on behalf of the use case and reported back to the code maintainers. The ESA SNAP⁷ software package was also installed. In this case SURF found a problem with the setup of SNAP, as maintained by ESA, in that the *.snap* configuration file overlaps with several other standard, pre-installed software packages in particular that of the popular CephFS filesystem that is also deployed on SURF's infrastructure. This problem was reported to ESA and together with ESA a workaround has been implemented. SNAP is now available on the SURF infrastructure and SURF has recommended ESA to change the naming of the hidden snap configuration files. A JupyterHub setup has also been deployed on the SURF infrastructure to support RETURN. It is expected that the S-2 part of this use case will analyse the full data set provided by EODC in Q3-4 of 2022. For the LSDA case SURF has provided support for containerization, enabled scrontab⁸ for automatic job scheduling and provided advice on deployment of the workflow on SURF's data processing infrastructure. It is expected that this use case will continue at SURF and scale up using additional resources at EODC.

VITO has supported the use of openEO in their installations for the WaterWatch and Aquamonitor use cases. Besides the provisioning of resources, VITO has provided extensive support for porting the use cases to the openEO framework ensuring the applications can run on the C-SCALE providers.

GRNET has been actively supporting - in terms of resources and technical support - the HiSea use case, for the period M01-M18. Two major facilities are provided: Cloud and HPC, both delivering CPU and storage resources. On the cloud, one VM with 16 cores is used for the pre- and post-processing in the use case and a second VM is deployed as an NFS-Server with an additional 300 TB storage for data caching. Moreover, in the HPC infrastructure, HiSea users have already access to run jobs on the "fat nodes" partition of the HPC infrastructure⁹ (40 cores per node). The initial VA consumption in this HPC infrastructure is attributable to the setup and testing of the system, such as calculating the scalability and the performance efficiency of the production code using Singularity¹⁰ containers. Currently, HiSea users are focusing on the pre-processing phase happening in the Cloud domain.

During M01-M18, CloudFerro became the resource provider of two projects so far: *Wetland Water Stress* and *SAR on the fly*. Both are in the early stage of development thus consumption of the resources is not very high yet. CloudFerro provides GPU for the needs of the *SAR on the fly* project, which helps to get results faster for their project. In the near future, it is expected that HiSea use case will start using GPU and CPU from CloudFerro. Additionally, a new kind of installation for delivering remote data access using S3 interface is currently under discussion and piloting. This new installation will support downloading data to other providers of the federation to enable the distributed processing of data.

⁶ <https://yeoda.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁷ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/tools/snap>

⁸ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/scrontab.html>

⁹ See technical description of nodes at <https://doc.aris.grnet.gr/system/hardware/#fat-nodes>

¹⁰ <https://sylabs.io/singularity>

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	17 of 21

INCD has deployed a Kubernetes cluster on top of an OpenStack cluster to support C-SCALE use cases. The Kubernetes cluster is composed of 5 nodes with 16 cores and 32 GB of RAM each where openEO is deployed. The first approach was to create a single volume of 12TB for the storage of data for the Aquamonitor use case, but it has been changed to a S3 bucket that is mounted on every single compute node, allowing for the sharing of data both within the cluster and the outside world. A local STAC server has been deployed to download satellite imagery products directly to a S3 Bucket which is then used by openEO. A python script was developed to register the metadata of the downloaded products in the user STAC catalogue available at CESNET, in this way all the data that is stored in our S3 bucket can be discovered on the catalogue at CESNET.

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	18 of 21

6 Green Computing

C-SCALE WP3's manages the tier-1 aspects of Green Computing of the project, defined as follows:

Tier 1: Analysis of the “Direct environmental OPEX” of C-SCALE by tracking the energy consumption of the computing centres. Monitoring of the KPIs (PUE and REF) defined in the EN-50600-4 across as many of the computing centres as possible and the use of additional indicators (such as reuse of the heat of the computing centre or carbon intensity of the electricity supply) where available.

Table 5 reports the available metrics for the providers for the green computing aspects wherever these are available.

Table 5. Green Computing aspects of the providers

Provider	Metrics	Comments
EODC	n/a	<p>Efficiency and environmentally responsible computing are a strong theme at EODC.</p> <p>To support this, the following measures are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Power supplies for storage and compute systems are either 80 Plus Platinum rated, or equivalent, following compliance with Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/424 (Directive 2009/125/EC). ● The primary datacentre makes use of a free cooling setup completed in 2019. This is further enhanced with turbo technology, whereby exhaust airflow is used to further improve efficiency. <p>The latest iteration of EODC HPC, based on the VSC-5 ranks at 90 in the Green 500 - An international ranking of supercomputer power efficiently - and offers 4.48 GFlops/Watts¹¹</p>
CESNET	PUE: 1.6	CESNET actively monitors energy consumption of production clusters.
INFN	n/a	INFN is actively studying measures to implement a green approach on running the ReCaS-Bari Data Centre. INFN is planning the implementation of a direct free cooling solution inside the data centre. In the short term INFN is deeply investing time in studying the optimization on cooling systems depending on the status of usage of the IT resources.
SURF	PUE: 1.22 REF: 1	<p>SURF tracks energy consumption of the data centres hosting C-SCALE workloads and is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure.</p> <p>SURF is not under direct control of the PUE and REF metrics of the data centres as SURF acts as a tenant for those.</p>

¹¹ See <https://www.top500.org/lists/green500/2022/06/>

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	19 of 21

VITO	n/a	VITO's computing resource supplier has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600. Moreover, with continuous performance improvements through OpenEO, VITO is aiming to reduce the need for computing resources for EO data processing.
GRNET	PUE: 1.6	GRNET is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure, while it measures the energy consumption of the data centres that deliver all the workloads.
CloudFerro	PUE: 1.65	CloudFerro's data centre for provisioning C-Scale resources has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600.
INCD	PUE: 1.45	<p>Since the early start of the INCD, reducing the carbon footprint of the infrastructure is one of the major goals. To accomplish this, over the last years, a series of investments and procedures have been implemented on the operational data centre. The measures were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Installation of new racks and replacement of the old supply circuits with new Power Distribution Units (PDU), with real-time consumption measures. The new PDU's effectively increase the efficiency of data centre power usage. ● Inclusion in public tendering specifications, CPU power consumption (SPEC per watt) and power supplies with 80 Plus Titanium certification. ● Implementation of free-cooling, requiring a re-design of the cooling system and chillers replacements by new units optimized to the climate conditions (subtropical in the case of Lisbon, Portugal).

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	20 of 21

7 Conclusions

All C-SCALE Virtual Access installations are now engaged with use cases of the project. The conditions and resources available for each use case are captured on Service Level Agreements documents, ensuring customers and providers have clear expectations on the delivered service and support the capacity planning of the project.

Until M11 the usage reported was mostly due to testing integration of the providers, in the period M11-M18 the infrastructure has started to be actively used by all the use cases. Still this usage is low due to the piloting and testing nature of the current use cases implementation phase. Once the use cases get to a production phase, the expected consumption will increase. Besides the use cases from the project, two new use cases from the Open Call have been already onboarded into the providers and the rest of the new use cases will start in the coming months as agreed with the use case representatives. The assignment of VA resources for the new use cases has been already discussed and agreed and captured in draft Service Level Agreements that will be finalised when the use cases are ready to start.

Doc. Name	Periodical assessment of the services V2				
Doc. Ref.	D3.5	Version	1.1	Page	21 of 21